

Islamic Teachings on Love of Homeland According to the Qur'an

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ABSTRACT

Love of the homeland is a very subtle and deep feeling in the human heart with which love of the homeland arises from true faith so as to cause the feeling to sacrifice for the glory of the motherland. The study of the concept of this discussion aims to foster a deep feeling of love for the homeland for a Muslim because it has been taught in the Qur'an. This research uses literature method with qualitative approach. The results showed that Islam has taught its adherents to love their homeland with the sources of evidence contained in the Qur'an. It can be said that Islam is a teaching that cares for the homeland so that its adherents must sacrifice and care for their homeland.

INTRODUCTION

A commendable attitude and good self-control in facing problems, as well as always maintaining harmony will create a peaceful environment and away from disputes so that the value of unity and unity will always be maintained. It is one of the effects of commendable morals that have an impact on maintaining the value of unity in the country so as to cause an attitude of love for the homeland based on commendable morals. (Harahap, 2022) Love of the homeland is an attitude of loving the homeland with all body and soul. This attitude of love for the homeland has been contonized by freedom fighters when Indonesia as our homeland was colonized by foreign nations. Independence heroes are willing to sacrifice property and lives for the independence of their homeland, Indonesia, for the sake of unity and unity. But the love of the homeland today does not have to be shown by attending military academies to participate in war, only with commendable morals, we can show our love for the motherland.(Risvan Akhir Roswandi, 2022)

The homeland we occupy is not only a place for ourselves in living life, but in it there are also other people who are also just like us, namely living their daily lives. In addition, there are also other creatures created by God in the form of animals, plants, and the environment that also inhabit our beloved homeland (Fuad, 2016). For this reason, there is a need for knowledge for humans to be able to live side by side with others in the same place, the same homeland, so that a harmonious life will be created, both fellow humans and with the natural environment around with a harmonious life, then indirectly we have also maintained unity and unity in our beloved homeland as a form of love for our homeland for our country, namely Indonesia.

THEORETICAL REVIEW

It is one of the effects of commendable morals that have an impact on maintaining the value of unity in the country so as to cause an attitude of love for the homeland based on commendable morals. (Harahap, 2022) Love of the homeland is an attitude of loving the homeland with all body and soul. This attitude of love for the homeland has been contonized by freedom fighters when Indonesia as our homeland was colonized by foreign nations. Independence heroes are willing to sacrifice property and lives for the independence of their homeland, Indonesia, for the sake of unity and unity. But the love of the homeland today does not have to be shown by attending military academies to participate in war, only with commendable morals, we can show our love for the motherland.(Risvan Akhir Roswandi, 2022)

METHODOLOGY

The research method used in this study uses a library research approach. Library *research is* research whose data collection is carried out by taking various literature materials from data contained from various existing reading sources. Various literature materials and information are taken both from books, papers, and information on the internet media. This study also used a study of Qur'anic verses as a source that discusses the problem.

The approach taken in this research is a qualitative approach. The qualitative approach is, By emphasizing its analysis on the process of conclusion, comparison, and on the analysis of the dynamics of the relationship of observed phenomena using scientific logic.(Wekke, 2022)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Understanding Love for the Motherland

In the Big Dictionary Indonesian the word love means very happy. While the word homeland has the meaning of the country of birth, spilled blood. From the two meanings of the word, it can be analyzed that love for the homeland is a feeling of love and affection for the homeland, the Indonesian state, which has given life and identity in the form of identity for someone, namely an Indonesian citizen.

Love for the Motherland is a behavior that shows care, appreciation, which is based on the spirit of nationality and is willing to sacrifice for the sake of the archipelago and the nation. The behavior of loving the homeland means loving domestic products, diligently studying for the progress of the nation and State, loving the environment, carrying out clean and healthy living, knowing the territory of the country without regional fanaticism. The attitude of love for each individual's homeland can be reflected through the behavior of their daily lives. In Indonesia, children are required to take education, because through education students are introduced and taught to know and love their country Indonesia. Love of the homeland is the same as love for the environment in which we live.(Atika et al., 2019)

Love of the homeland should be widely understood and understood its purpose and purpose. Love of the homeland is also often known as nationalism. Nationalism is a belief held by individuals and a number of people, so that they form a nationality organized in one area of government; Nationalism is a sense of community as a nation(Chaniago et al., 2020). In summary, nationalism is a nationalism which is the highest loyalty of individuals to their nation and homeland. Love of the homeland is essentially an inseparable part of every human being. As the understanding of love for the homeland in the previous section, love for the homeland is synonymous with the term nationalism. (Ikhsan, 2017)

(Khikmah, 2021) Love of the homeland is a sense of pride for the nation in language, culture, social, politics and economy so that it is willing to sacrifice to defend, protect, and advance the nation consciously without any coercion from anyone. That way, whatever this nation and country have, citizens are obliged to love and take care of it

Love of the homeland means the willingness to sacrifice for the glory of the motherland, love of one's own nation and country, be proud of one's national identity, and make it a force to become a better person and benefit the surrounding humans. This love will continue to be attached to a citizen even though he is in a distant place or different countries, because there is a cultural identity.

The homeland is where a person returns Just like home wherever people will go, in the end the person will also return to his home, which is the homeland of Indonesia.

There are obligations for citizens as a form of love for their homeland towards their country. Everyone must agree that protecting and caring for the environment and surroundings is an obligation for everyone, and it is an unwritten obligation for citizens to their country. A clean environment, nature that is maintained will provide benefits for humans themselves so that it will provide peace and harmony in human relations with nature. However, if the environment is not well cared for, even neglected, it will cause harm to humans themselves.

Love of the homeland is a natural human character. Because it is in that homeland that they are born, raised, educated and loved. The feeling of longing for the homeland shows the love and inner connection between man and his homeland. Love for the homeland will cause nationalism, namely awareness and spirit of love for the motherland.

Said that the cultivation of a sense of love for the homeland can be pursued through education, precisely character education. Character education is called ethics education, moral education, value education, character education, moral education which aims to develop the ability of educated humans to determine good and bad, maintain what is good and apply that good in life.

Said that in the Islamic perspective, there are two words that are usually associated with the idea of nationalism: *al-Wataniyan* and *al-Qawmiyah*. According to al-Banna, the meaning of these two words in the context of nationality is, *al-Wathaniyah* is equivalent to the word patriotism which means love of the motherland. This concept is based on certain spaces, residences, and homelands. The relationship to identity is *given* or in sociological theory as an acquired status (*ascribed status*). The word *al-Qawmiyah* means pride and citizenship, a sense of belonging to the unity of political society achieved and achieved through certain struggles. This concept refers to a person or group of people, usually united by a certain ideology, vision, mission, and aspirations to achieve a common goal.

Factors Growing Love for the Motherland

Historical equality emerged as an element of nationality because this element is one of the most important in order to unite people's feelings, thoughts, and steps. History is important because people, nations, and groups can see the positive or negative effects of past experiences, then take lessons from history to move into a better and prosperous future. The glorious history of a group will be proud of its members and descendants, and vice versa.

The Qur'an is very prominent in describing historical events. In fact, the main purpose of the historical description is to take i'tibar (lessons), in order to determine the next step. In short, it can be said that the historical element is in line with the teachings of the Quran. So that if this element is used as one of the factors for the birth of national understanding, it is inclusive in the teachings of the Qur'an, as long as the historical description is directed to achieve goodness, harmony, and welfare.

Love of the motherland is part of faith

According to human nature is to love the place where he grew up. So it is not strange if someone wants to live old in his birthplace. To love one's homeland is to love one's own nation. There is a lot of historical evidence that the prophet Abraham always thought, tried and prayed that his homeland would be safe, peaceful, and blessed. One of the prayers offered by the prophet Abraham, Allah enshrined in the Qur'an:

وَإِذْ قَالَ إِبْرَاهِيمُ رَبِّ اجْعَلْ هَذَا بَلَدًا ءَامِنًا وَاَرْزُقْ أَهْلَهُ مِنْ الثَّمَرَاتِ مَنْ ءَامَنَ مِنْهُمْ بِاللَّهِ
وَالْيَوْمِ الْآخِرِ ...

"And (remember), when Abraham prayed: 'O my Lord, make this land, a land of salvation sentosa, and give sustenance of fruit to its inhabitants who believe among them in Allah and the day after...". (QS. Al Baqoroh: 126)

Prophet Ibrohim prayed for his homeland:

- 1) Become a safe country sentosa.
- 2) The population is overflowing with rizqi.
- 3) The people have faith in Allah and the last days.

This shows that Prophet Ibrohim was someone who had a deep love for his homeland.

There is a postulate from the Qur'an related to love of the motherland, which affirms that love of the homeland is a very strong natural impulse in the human self and soul. He said this when interpreting God's word:

وَلَوْ أَنَّا كَتَبْنَا عَلَيْهِمْ أَنْ اقْتُلُوا أَنْفُسَكُمْ أَوْ احْرُجُوا مِنْ دِيَارِكُمْ مَا فَعَلُوهُ إِلَّا قَلِيلٌ مِّنْهُمْ وَلَوْ أَنَّهُمْ
فَعَلُوا مَا يُوعَظُونَ بِهِ لَكَانَ خَيْرًا لَّهُمْ وَأَشَدَّ تَنبِيئًا

And verily if We had commanded them, "Kill yourselves or get you out of your village", they would not have done so except a small part of them. And indeed if they carry out the lessons that are given to them, surely it is better for them and more strengthening (their faith). (QS. An Nisa: 66)

Fakhruddin al-Razi commented, "Allah made leaving one's hometown the level of suicide." It is as if God were saying: "If I had commanded them one of the two greatest difficulties in the universe, surely they would not have done it. The two biggest difficulties in the universe are suicide or leaving home." Leaving home, for a reasonable person, is a very difficult thing to do, just as painful as suicide. This shows that love for the homeland has a very deep meaning for humans.

The above verses and interpretations show how precious a homeland is, in the view of the Qur'an to the point that expulsion from the homeland is juxtaposed with the killing of life or even more severe and cruel. Therefore, when mentioning the sacred duty of jihad, the Qur'an often connects and juxtaposes it with defending the homeland from the clutches of invaders.

In the principle of nationalism, Hasan al-Bana establishes that our nationalism focuses on total loyalty (wala') to Allah and his Messenger and to believers. We find this a lot in the Qur'an and Hadith.

From the verses of the Qur'an it can be concluded that:

- 1) Proud of the blasphemy in terms of nationalism and history and the retracing of pious salafus by the younger generation.
- 2) The priority scale of nationalism's attention to the birth of virtues for them.
- 3) Fighting pride in ethnicity, nationality and jahiliyah traditions.
- 4) Understand our nationalism on complete loyalty to Allah, his Messenger and the believers. (Rashidin, 2022)

A sense of nationality cannot be expressed without being proven by patriotism and love of the motherland. Love of the homeland does not contradict religious principles, it is even contained in the teachings of the Qur'an and the practice of the Prophet Muhammad *صلى الله عليه وسلم*.

Character Love Motherland

Love for the homeland must be instilled in children from an early age so that as the next generation of the nation can realize attitudes and behaviors that are beneficial to the interests of society and avoid social deviations that can damage Indonesian cultural norms and values. The cultivation of the character of love for the homeland is carried out, considering that this nation needs a better generation in the future. The existence of local content education will make students more aware of their culture. (Nurdian et al., 2021)

One of the positive values that need to be instilled in students at school is the character of love for the motherland. Given the reality that exists today, many among the younger generation have begun to fade their love for the country. (Atika et al., 2019). The low values of love for the homeland are due to the negative influence of western culture that enters Indonesia. The values of love for the homeland need to be instilled from an early age so that as the successor of the nation can realize attitudes and behaviors that are beneficial to the interests of the community. The school, especially teachers, is expected to

find ways to increase the love of the country so that students have noble morals, healthy, intelligent, skills, achievements and competitiveness have a commitment to show the nation. (David & Triadi, 2021)

Nationalist character values are ways of thinking, behaving, and acting that show loyalty, care, and high respect for the language, physical, social, cultural, economic, and political environment of the nation, placing the interests of the nation and state above the interests of themselves and their groups. (Audina et al., 2022). Basic character is a human nature trait that is believed to be formed and developed through certain educational methods such as character education. The implementation of education can formulate basic characters that will be developed in accordance with the values of certain nations or religions. (Primary, 2022)

Love for the homeland is one of the character values that needs to be instilled in learning at school, because it is related to the implementation of the rights and obligations of learners in the effort to defend the country. One of the factors that influence the attitude of love for the homeland is the lack of understanding of the history of the nation's struggle. One way to instill the value of love for the homeland in learning at school is to instill a sense of pride, care, loyalty and high appreciation for the country which is delivered not just material in subjects, or only directed at academic lessons that emphasize learning outcomes (Hasanah et al., 2022). In developing character education for love for the motherland, a joint understanding is needed between the government, educational institutions, educators, teachers and parents, as well as the community about the importance of building the character of love for the homeland (Fadiyah Nur Afifah et al., 2022)

People Who Really Love the Motherland

If we look around us, those who damage the homeland are actually people who tout nationalist ideas. That is, those who declare themselves to be defenders of the motherland, defenders of unity and unity. Isn't shirk and inaction, corruption cases, forest clearing projects, environmental pollution, oppression, arbitrariness and everything else done by so-called nationalists? Politicians who persistently defend the idea of love for the motherland. Even though love for the homeland without being based on the right science will only cause damage. God I said:

ظَهَرَ الْفَسَادُ فِي الْبَرِّ وَالْبَحْرِ بِمَا كَسَبَتْ أَيْدِي النَّاسِ لِيُذِيقَهُمْ بَعْضَ الَّذِي عَمِلُوا لَعَلَّهُمْ
يَرْجِعُونَ

It has been seen that corruption on land and in the sea is caused by the works of human hands, so that Allah may feel to them a part of their deeds, that they may return (to the right path). (QS. Ar Ruum : 41)

(Maragustam, 2021) said that human relationships with the surrounding environment, influence each other (interactive). Humans can be formed in character or character tuna. For in essence the human soul is like a ta (Hasanah et

al., 2022) Well clay, which is ready to be forged in any form. From religious spirituality gives birth to the values of integrity (honesty-trust), responsibility, love of the motherland, mutual respect, humility, tolerance towards harmony, social care, love of knowledge, hard work, patience, independence, and friendship.

وَإِذَا قِيلَ لَهُمْ لَا تُفْسِدُوا فِي الْأَرْضِ قَالُوا إِنَّمَا نَحْنُ مُصْلِحُونَ

And when it was said to them, "Do not cause mischief on the face of the earth".

They answered: "Verily we are the ones who make improvements". (QS. Al Baqarah: 11)

Destruction on earth is an activity that causes something that fulfills its values and or functions properly and is useful to lose part or all of its value so that it does not or decreases its function and benefits. A person is required, at the very least, to be godly, that is, to maintain the values of something so that its condition remains unchanged as it is, and thus that something continues to function properly and beneficially.

Cover

Love of the motherland is a very subtle and deep feeling in the human heart. In fact, love for the homeland arises from true faith. Since it is a natural human feeling, its presence is without having to be forced and asked. The patriot spirit is a logical consequence that arises from souls who understand the meaning of nation and state.

Love of the homeland in Islam is a feeling of longing for the homeland that shows the love and inner relationship between humans and their homeland, accompanied by good behavior or morality to AllahI, to others and also to their environment, so as not to cause damage caused by themselves. Love for the homeland will cause nationalism, namely awareness and spirit of love for the motherland. Nationalism that is true and in accordance with religious law will have a positive impact on the perpetrators.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Love for the Motherland is a behavior that shows care, appreciation, which is based on the spirit of nationality and is willing to sacrifice for the sake of the archipelago and the nation. The behavior of loving the homeland means loving domestic products, diligently studying for the progress of the nation and State, loving the environment, carrying out clean and healthy living, knowing the territory of the country without regional fanaticism. The attitude of love for each individual's homeland can be reflected through the behavior of their daily lives. In Indonesia, children are required to take education, because through education students are introduced and taught to know and love their country Indonesia. Love of the homeland is the same as love for the environment in which we live.(Atika et al., 2019)

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